

Making the casein supplement from skim milk

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the feasibility of producing casein, a nutritious protein supplement, from skim milk using household methods. Casein is a rich source of calcium, essential for bone and heart health, and contains 18 amino acids, including all 9 essential amino acids that the human body cannot synthesize. The research compared home-based techniques with laboratory methods for extracting casein, focusing on yield and purity across different drying processes: freeze-drying, laboratory oven drying at 40°C, 50°C, 60°C, and household convection oven drying at 50°C. Results showed that freeze-drying produced casein powder with the highest protein content at 82.69%. The household convection oven method was more efficient than laboratory oven drying. With a drying time of 6 hours, the household method yielded 20 grams of casein powder per liter of skim milk, with a protein content of 76.15%. This work supports the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 3: *Good Health and Well-Being*, which aims to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages, by providing an accessible and natural source of high-quality protein. It also contributes to Sustainable Development Goal 9: *Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure*, by encouraging small-scale, innovative approaches to protein production as alternatives to conventional industrial methods.

KEYWORDS: Casein, skim milk, household technique, drying method, supplement

1. INTRODUCTION

Livestock farming is a major source of milk in Mongolia, which ranks 58th in the world for cattle population, providing a potential for milk production.¹ Skim milk is often regarded as waste after fat separation in sour cream production, which contains valuable protein and calcium in the form of calcium caseinate. Casein is a slow-digesting protein containing 18 amino acids, including 9 essential ones that the body cannot produce.² Therefore, this research focused on exploring methods for extracting casein from skim milk using a household convection oven. The study compared household casein extraction methods with a laboratory technique³, assessing yield and purity through various drying methods: freeze-drying, laboratory oven drying, and household convection oven drying. Nowadays, many people rely on industrial casein supplements, which contain artificial synthetic materials. This household method for extracting casein from skim milk offers an eco-friendly, innovative alternative to commercial casein supplements. Home-extracted casein can provide a natural, sustainable protein source, meeting daily protein needs of approximately 0.75 grams per kilogram of body weight, thus reducing reliance on synthetic supplements.⁴

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Extraction of casein from milk

A 250 mL sample of skim milk was treated with approximately 1 g of citric acid. The mixture was placed in a water bath at 60°C and stirred until curds formed. Used a thermometer to ensure milk was heated to an appropriate temperature (around 40-50°C or 104-122°F) for curdling. The curd was then filtered and dried in a laboratory oven at 40, 50, or 60°C, or in a freeze-dryer, or in a household convection oven. Once dried, the curd was ground into powder for convenient use.

- Freeze-drying method: The prepared curd sample was placed in the freezer (Haier biomedical DW86L728J) to cool down to -80 °C, and then transferred to the freeze-dryer in a vacuum pump (EYELA - FDU-1200).
- Laboratory oven drying method: The heat dryer (Heat-drier- XMTA-6000) was first preheated to the desired temperature, then the wet curd sample was placed into the heat dryer, and the mass was recorded at 2-hour intervals.
- Household convection oven drying method: Casein was dried using a fan-assisted household convection oven (Hansa BCCI616234) set to 50°C. The sample used was skim milk with 0.4% fat content.

2.2 Determination of casein content⁵

The 0.5 g residue sample was placed into a 250 mL test tube. The following reagents were then added: 3.4 g of catalyst (a mixture of 97.2% K₂SO₄, 2.8% CuSO₄·5H₂O) and 10 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid (96-98%). The samples were digested for 30 minutes at 150°C, followed by 90 mins at 200°C, 30 mins at 300°C, and 120 mins at 420°C. After digestion, the test tubes were allowed to cool to 40-50°C. Next, the digested samples were transferred to a Kjeldahl distillation and titration apparatus using the following solutions:

- Distilled water was added to bring the total volume to 100 mL
- 0.1 N HCl was used as the titrant.
- 15 mL of 40% NaOH was added, along with 3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator.
- 20 mL of 2% H₃BO₃ solution was prepared with 3 drops of Tashiro's indicator.

Finally, the casein content was calculated using the following formula⁶:

$$(\text{Protein}\%) = \frac{(\text{mL standard acid} - \text{mL blank}) \times N \text{ of acid} \times 1.4007}{\text{Weight of sample in grams}} \times \text{Dilution factor} * 6.38$$

2.3 Determination of fat content in dry sample

The dry mass of samples (approximately 3 g is recommended) was measured and wrapped in a paper envelope. The sample was then placed in a Soxhlet extractor containing 250 mL of hexane. The extractor was connected to a Florence flask positioned on a heating mantle set at 100°C, with a condenser mounted on top to prevent hexane loss. After 2 hours of extraction cycle, the samples were transferred to a drying oven to remove any remaining the hexane, then weighed again. Finally, the fat content was calculated by using the following formula:

$$(\text{Fat}\%) = \frac{(\text{initial mass} - \text{final mass})}{\text{Initial mass}} \times 100$$

2.4 Determination of moisture content in dried curd or powdered casein

The 5 g of samples were measured with a weighing bottle. The prepared sample was then placed in a drying oven, and its mass was recorded at 2-hour intervals. Once the mass stabilized, the moisture was calculated using the following formula:

$$(\text{moisture}\%) = \frac{(\text{weighing bottle with sample mass} - \text{weighing bottle mass})}{(\text{weighing bottle with sample mass after stabilized} - \text{weighing bottle mass})} \times 100$$

2.5 Safety & Ethics

Use clean, sanitized equipment to avoid contamination during the process. When heating milk to separate the casein, always monitor the temperature carefully. High temperatures could result in scalding, and overheating may lead to undesirable chemical reactions. Be cautious when handling citric acid, as it can cause irritation or burns if it comes into contact with skin or eyes. Always wear protective gloves and goggles when handling acids or hot liquids. Dispose of any waste (like leftover whey or used materials) in an environmentally friendly way. Avoid pouring anything down the drain that could clog or damage plumbing.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Laboratory oven drying and Freeze-drying

The drying temperature and the time it consumed had a significant impact on the quality, appearance, and stability of the casein samples. Drying at 40°C required an extended period and was still incomplete after 24 hours, with samples retaining notable moisture levels, which compromised their stability for storage. In contrast, drying at 60°C reduced the time compared to 40°C (Table 1). However, the high temperature caused the casein to turn yellow and resulted in a hard, brittle texture that was difficult to crush, indicating possible protein degradation (Figure 2).

Drying at 50°C produced more favourable results. It required a drying time similar to that of 60°C, therefore, similar energy usage. Also, it caused less discoloration. The texture remained firm, yet manageable, suggesting that 50°C strikes a balance between efficiency and product quality.

As a control, freeze-drying resulted in a perfect white sample, with no visible signs of fat oxidation or casein decomposition (Figure 3). While this method preserves high quality, it is less accessible for home use due to its equipment requirements.

Based on these results, drying at 50°C appeared to be the most effective method for producing high-quality casein at home. It offers a practical balance between drying time, colour retention, and texture, making it suitable for affordable production at home.

Table 1. Laboratory oven drying of skim milk with 0.1, 0.4, 2% fat content at 40-60°C

Drying time (hours)	Average remaining mass in grams (\pm SD)								
	Skim milk with 0.1% fat content			Skim milk with 0.4% fat content			Skim milk with 2% fat content		
	40°C	50°C	60°C	40°C	50°C	60°C	40°C	50°C	60°C
0	22 \pm 4	25 \pm 2	26 \pm 2	15.9 \pm 0.6	14.6 \pm 0.8	18 \pm 1	18.6 \pm 0.7	18.1 \pm 0.6	20 \pm 3
2	21 \pm 4	23 \pm 2	23 \pm 2	14.4 \pm 0.7	12.6 \pm 0.8	14.7 \pm 0.8	17.2 \pm 0.9	16.0 \pm 0.8	12 \pm 2
4	21 \pm 4	22 \pm 1	20 \pm 2	13.7 \pm 0.7	11.3 \pm 0.9	12.1 \pm 0.6	16.0 \pm 0.9	14.0 \pm 0.9	10 \pm 2
6	20 \pm 4	19 \pm 1	17 \pm 2	12.9 \pm 0.8	10 \pm 1	10.0 \pm 0.5	15 \pm 1	13 \pm 1	9 \pm 1
8	19 \pm 4	17 \pm 1	14 \pm 2	12.1 \pm 0.9	8.8 \pm 0.9	8.4 \pm 0.4	14 \pm 1	10.7 \pm 0.8	9 \pm 1
10	18 \pm 4	15 \pm 1	11 \pm 1	11.3 \pm 0.9	7.8 \pm 0.7	7.6 \pm 0.3	12 \pm 1	8.7 \pm 0.6	
12	18 \pm 4	13 \pm 1	8.8 \pm 0.5	10.7 \pm 0.9	7.3 \pm 0.5	7.2 \pm 0.3	8.1 \pm 0.2		

Figure 1. Average remaining mass in grams of milk curd during laboratory oven drying at 40-60°C (a) milk curd from skim milk with 0.1% fat content (b) milk curd from skim milk with 0.4% fat content (c) milk curd from skim milk with 2% fat content

Figure 2. The colour of milk curd (a) before and (b) after drying in a laboratory oven at 40°C for 10 hours.

Figure 3. Comparison of curd powder obtained from freeze-drying (left) and laboratory oven drying at 60, 50, 40°C (left to right)

3.2 Convection oven drying at home

The kitchen oven used for homemade method was a convection oven equipped with a heat-distribution fan. Using convection oven drying at home at 50°C, 0.4 % fat skim milk reached a stable mass after 6 hours drying (Table 2), which was faster than the 10-hour required in the laboratory heating oven (Figure 1b). The final mass was approximately 38% of the original weight (Table 2), which was similar to the remaining mass percentage observed when 0.4% fat milk curd was dried in a laboratory hot oven at 60°C for 12 hours. Since an average of 5 grams of casein powder was obtained from 250 mL of milk, the household method yielded approximately 20 grams per liter of milk.

Table 2 Convection oven drying of skim milk with 0.4% fat content at home.

Drying time (hours)	Remaining mass (grams)					SD
	No.1	No.2	No.3	No.4	Average	
0	14	14	11	13	13	1
2	7	7	5	6	6	0.8
4	6	6	5	5	6	0.5
6	5	6	4	5	5	0.7
8	5	6	4	5	5	0.7
10	5	6	4	5	5	0.7
12	5	6	4	5	5	0.7

Figure 4. Mass change during convection oven drying of a 0.4% fat milk at 50°C.

3.3 Protein content

The Kjeldahl method is a widely used technique for determining nitrogen content in organic substances, based on the digestion of the sample with concentrated sulfuric acid and a catalyst to convert nitrogen into ammonium sulfate. This is followed by neutralization with a strong base, distillation of released ammonia, and titration to quantify the nitrogen content. In the analysis of casein in milk powder, the Kjeldahl method was used to measure total nitrogen, which was then converted to protein content using a conversion factor of 6.38. Since casein is the major protein in milk, the measured nitrogen primarily reflects the casein content, making the method suitable for assessing protein quality and quantity in dairy products.

The 0.1% fat milk had a higher protein content than the 0.4% and 2% fat samples, respectively (Table 3). The freeze-drying method yielded the highest protein content, with 82.69% for the 0.4% fat milk – complying with the GOST 31689-2012 standards, which specify a minimum of 80% protein purity and a maximum moisture content of 4.98%. In contrast, laboratory oven drying resulted in lower protein content, ranging from 49% to 70%, with higher drying temperatures leading to lower protein values. The homemade casein powder prepared using a convection oven with fan-assisted drying achieved a protein content of 76.15%, which was higher than that obtained using the laboratory oven method (Figure 5).

Table 3 Protein content in the casein powder

Drying method	Temperature	Protein content (%)		
		Milk with 0.1 % fat	Milk with 0.4 % fat	Milk with 2 % fat
Heat drying	40°C	76.64	70.30	68.53
	50°C	73.88	66.20	66.79
	60°C	75.06	49.49	60.40
Freeze-dried	-		82.69	70.25
Fan-assisted oven at home	50°C		76.15	

Figure 5. Protein content in dried milk curd obtained from Kjeldahl method.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Our investigation comparing various drying methods revealed that drying at 50°C provided the most suitable texture for end-user processing. The home-based method of convection oven drying at 50°C offered the best balance of efficiency and quality. Convection oven drying of milk with 0.4% fat content yielded 20 grams of powder per liter. The product was a low-moisture, high-purity casein powder with a protein content of 76.15%. While freeze-drying remains the gold standard for preserving protein structure, it is impractical for home use. Compared to conventional oven drying, fan-assisted drying improved water removal and minimized heat damage, making it a more efficient and protein-friendly technique for household applications. This research demonstrated the feasibility of producing a natural, additive-free protein supplement at home using simple tools and methods. Looking ahead, we plan to integrate a milk-cream separator to efficiently produce skim milk from whole milk for future extractions. Additionally, we aim to study the long-term stability of casein under various storage conditions to further enhance its practical use.

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Author Contributions

K.M contributed to the conception, conducted the experiments and drafting of the manuscript. A.N. contributed to the data analysis, manuscript and conducted the experiments. M.T. contributed to the design and conducted the experiments.

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